

Comparative analysis of Chlorosarcinopsis eremi mitochondrial genome with some Chlamydomonadales algae

Fatemeh Khani-Juyabad¹, Parisa Mohammadi^{*1}, Mahbubeh Zarrabi¹

1 -Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Biological Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

2- Department of Biotechnology, Faculty of Biological Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

Abstract

Chlorosarcinopsis eremi is a member of Chlamydomonadales algae which is isolated from terrestrial environments. In this study, the mitochondrial genome of *C. eremi* isolated from desert region of Iran, was represented for the first time. Following sequencing, assembly and annotation, comparative analyses of *C. eremi* and other available Chlamydomonadales algae complete mitochondrial genomes were performed. The mitochondrial genome of *C. eremi* was circular, had a low number of genes coding in the same strand with a minor amount of repeated sequences; same as other non-Reinhardtinia species of Chlamydomonadales algae. GC content of *C. eremi* mitochondrial genome was in normal range when compared with non-Chlamydomonadales organisms, but among Chlamydomonadales algae, *C. eremi* had a low GC content mitochondrial genome. *C. eremi* had the highest percent of non-coding sequences in comparison with other available Chlamydomonadales mitochondrial genomes which was related to intergenic regions. Identity analysis of protein-coding sequences of Chlamydomonadales mitochondrial genomes showed more divergences and may be related to the high mutation rate of mitochondrial genome reported in microbial eukaryotes.

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